

- e) increasing the budget of teachers' free time;
- e) organization of systematic practical lessons on the exchange of experience between teachers of foreign languages
- g) a constant increase in qualified assistance to teachers undergoing advanced training and systematic monitoring of their self-education activities with

The creation of a teacher training system will contribute to the improvement of foreign language teaching, which in turn will contribute to the education of the younger generation, i.e. the realization of the task set for the school by the party and the Government to form a comprehensively developed.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO POPULARIZE HISTORICAL CITIES IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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Annotation: Uzbekistan is famous for such historical cities as Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. They have rich history, architecture and attractive monuments for tourists. Developing routes that cover these cities and their attractions will allow tourists to experience the unique culture and history of Uzbekistan. There are many architectural monuments in Uzbekistan that are part of the world cultural treasure. Historical monuments, rich in old cultural and architectural monuments, are

incomparable in terms of promoting tourism in Uzbekistan and raising it to new levels.

Аннотация: Узбекистан славится такими историческими городами, как Самарканд, Бухара и Хива. Они имеют богатую историю, архитектуру и привлекательные для туристов памятники. Разработка маршрутов, охватывающих эти города и их достопримечательности, позволит туристам приобщиться к уникальной культуре и истории Узбекистана. В Узбекистане множество памятников архитектуры, являющихся частью мирового культурного достояния. Исторические памятники, богатые старинными культурными и архитектурными памятниками, бесподобны с точки зрения развития туризма в Узбекистане и поднятия его на новый уровень.

Annotatsiya: O'zbekiston Samarqand, Buxoro, Xiva kabi tarixiy shaharlari bilan mashhur. Ularning boy tarixi, arxitekturasi va sayyohlar uchun jozibali yodgorliklari bor. Ushbu shaharlar va ularning diqqatga sazovor joylarini qamrab oluvchi marshrutlarni ishlab chiqish sayyohlarga O'zbekistonning betakror madaniyati va tarixi bilan tanish. O'zbekistonda jahon madaniyati xazinasiga kiruvchi ko'plab arxitektura yodgorliklari mavjud. O'zbekistonda turizmni rivojlantirish va uni yangi bosqichlarga ko'tarish borasida avvalo ko'hna madaniy va arxitektura yodgorliklariga boy bo'lgan tarixiy obidalarning o'rni va ahamiyati beqiyos.

Keywords: Historical cities, ancient monuments of the East, Organization of the Islamic Conference (OIC), International Islamic Organization (ISESCO), the main history and architectural monuments of historical cities, tourist zone.

Ключевые слова: Исторические города, древние памятники Востока, Организация Исламская конференция (ОИК), Международная исламская организация (ИСЕСКО), основные памятники истории и архитектуры исторических городов, туристическая зона

Kalit so'zlar: tarixiy shaharlar, Sharqning qadimiy obidalari, Islom konferensiyasi tashkiloti (OIK), Xalqaro islom tashkiloti (ISESCO), tarixiy shaharlarning asosiy tarixiy va me'moriy yodgorliklari, erkin turistik zona

Everyone living in different parts of the world lives in the dream of seeing these cities with their own eyes, because these historical cities are rich in monuments that show the culture of Uzbekistan and tell about the historical importance of the past of Uzbekistan. In many countries, Uzbekistan is famous for these cities. The historical centers of the cities of Khiva, Bukhara and Shahrizabz, historical monuments of ancient Samarkand are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. In 2012, a total of 962 objects of the world were included in the main list of UNESCOs "World Heritage", four of them are historical cities of Uzbekistan, which is 0.4% of the total

number. In these cities, there are ancient historical monuments that amaze and amaze the people of the whole world. Tashkent - one of the largest cities of Central Asia - is the capital of the Republic of Uzbekistan. International Islamic Organization for Education, Science and Culture ISESSO, one of the institutions within the Organization of the Islamic Conference, announced Tashkent as the capital of Islamic culture in 2007. Tashkent received such a high and proud title for its unparalleled services to the Islamic culture and science of Uzbekistan, preservation and further enrichment of Islamic heritage and monuments. Having said that, it is interesting that Tashkent region has a huge tourist potential. For example, the region has natural conditions for the development of extreme and mountain tourism, i.e. sledding, snowboarding, cycling, motor sports and extreme sports, as well as ecological and agricultural tourism. In particular, in the mountains of the Tashkent region, there is the Charvoq reservoir, on its shores there are many boarding houses, recreation areas and children's sports health camps. In addition, there are many museums in Tashkent. For example, the Museum of Fine Arts has the largest collection of sculptures, paintings and handicrafts in Central Asia. The Museum of Applied Arts of Uzbekistan has collected more than thirty thousand examples of crafts and people's national heritage. The State Museum of the History of the Timurids is a museum that contains all the examples of the history of the Timurid period. Osman's Koran and Beruni's library, included in the list of "Monuments of World Culture", are kept in Tashkent. As we all know, the earliest information about Tashkent can be found in ancient Chinese chronicles in the second century BC. As we know from history, the suburbs of Tashkent used to be called Choch. Choch is located at the crossroads of gold, precious stones, spices and magnificent horses from different countries. Today, Tashkent is a developed modern industrial city that reminds of the historical past of Uzbekistan. Samarkand is a "polished land" that attracts the attention of the world public with its delicacies, nature, rich spiritual heritage, unique history, and extensive architectural monuments. It is not for nothing that the eyes of notable investors of the world, famous businessmen and bankers of developed countries, heads of international organizations, economists and politicians, and art critics are focused on Samarkand today. This indicates that Samarkand has made an important contribution to the prosperity and development of the country, as the position of a major industrial, scientific and cultural center of Uzbekistan is increasing. Samarkand is a historical city in Uzbekistan with a history of 2750 years. We have a lot of historical information and historical facts about this city. All of them contribute to the development of tourism in Uzbekistan and are of great importance for the further growth of tourism potential.

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THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SPHERE

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Annotation: The service sector encompasses a broad range of industries that provide products and services to customers. From banking, hospitality, transportation, healthcare, and retailing, the service sector plays a key role in the global economy. One key factor that enables this sector to become successful is the ability to provide services to a diverse customer base. For this reason, the importance and prospects of learning foreign languages in the service sector cannot be overstated.

Аннотация: Сфера услуг охватывает широкий спектр отраслей, предоставляющих клиентам продукцию и услуги. Сектор услуг, начиная от банковского дела, гостиничного бизнеса, транспорта, здравоохранения и розничной торговли, играет ключевую роль в мировой экономике. Одним из ключевых факторов, который позволяет этому сектору добиться успеха, является способность предоставлять услуги разнообразной клиентской базе. По этой причине важность и перспективы изучения иностранных языков в сфере услуг невозможно переоценить.

Annotatsiya: Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi iste'molchilarga mahsulot va xizmatlarni taqdim etadigan keng doiradagi tarmoqlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bank, mehmondo'stlik, transport, sog'liqni saqlash va chakana savdodan tortib, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi jahon iqtisodiyotida asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu sektorning muvaffaqiyatli bo'lishiga imkon beruvchi asosiy omillardan biri bu turli xil mijozlar bazasiga xizmat ko'rsatish qobiliyatidir. Shu sababli, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida chet tillarini o'rganishning ahamiyati va istiqbolini ortiqcha baholab bo'lmaydi.